
CHALLENGES IN TEACHING LISTENING TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract: The students have limited vocabulary to understand the listening text. Furthermore students have limited time to listening exposure. Their listening exposure is still at the level of words and sentences. Difficulties in preparing the listening material based in syllabus. Most teachers feels that time management become their major challenge in organizing classroom. They have set lesson plan, but sometimes the lesson does not work exactly the same. They have to work with mixed-level students, with students with learning difficulties, and with learners who are coming from different backgrounds. Teachers should be aware that it is part of teachers' primary duty to cope with every student. Most students can learn a foreign language to some level, but there are many reasons why their improvements are not achieved significantly.

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For the speakers of other languages, learning English is a challenging process. There are many aspects that influence the success of learning English. One of the essential aspects is the learning material. Although the access to international

communication is widely open on line through internet, there is no clear rule or regulation on how to use those facilities for language education. In communicating by using foreign language, the EFL learners in Indonesia need some efforts in understanding and responding on the words they have just listen to. They need time before they could grasp the meaning of the words, especially if they are not in the level of the language proficiencies. Limitation of vocabulary has become their major difficulties in listening comprehension. Brown (2007) states that in teaching is on the awareness of teachers to teach language not only on the level of linguistics rules and definition, but they should encourage student to communicate spontaneously and meaningful. To be able to communicate spontaneously and meaningful, students should have appropriate language competence. Nunan (2002) says that Listening as one of the language skill is essential not only as a receptive skill but also to the development of spoken language proficiency. Listening skill of second language is not derived naturally; it needs some processes of learning. The processes of listening in the classroom involve active interaction between teachers and students. In listening classroom, teacher can be the source of the listening itself or becoming the instructor and the manager. A lot of listening materials are derived from recorded extract, for instance on CD, tape record, video and others.

Richard (2008) sees listening in two different perspectives; listening as comprehension and listening as acquisition. Listening for comprehension is the traditional nature of listening. This views listening as the process of understanding the meaning in a spoken discourse, while listening for acquisition focus on listening as the process of deriving other skill such as speaking. In understanding text as spoken discourse, Richards (2008: 4-7) introduces two different kind of processes. They are often referred to as bottom-up and top-down processing. Bottom-up processing refers to the use of the incoming input as the basis for understanding the message. Comprehension begins with the received data that is analyzed at the levels of organization – sounds, words, clauses, sentences, texts–until meaning is derived.

Comprehension is viewed as a process of decoding. While Top-down processing, on the other hand, refers to the use of background knowledge in understanding the meaning of a message. Whereas bottom-up processing goes from language to meaning, top-down processing goes from meaning to language. The background knowledge required for topdown processing may be previous knowledge about the topic of discourse, situational or contextual knowledge, or knowledge in the form of “schemata” or “scripts”—plans about the overall structure of events and the relationships between them. When it comes to some important bullet points of teaching language:

1. Limited Attention Span

- **Challenge:** Young learners often struggle to focus for extended periods, making it hard to maintain their attention during listening activities.
- **Solution:** Use short, engaging activities like songs, games, or storytelling. Incorporate frequent breaks or transitions to maintain interest.

2. Vocabulary and Language Limitations

- **Challenge:** Young learners may not yet have a strong grasp of the language, which can make understanding spoken input difficult.
- **Solution:** Pre-teach key vocabulary and use visuals, gestures, and context clues to support comprehension. Gradually introduce more complex language as they become familiar.

3. Difficulty Differentiating Sounds

- **Challenge:** Young learners may struggle to differentiate similar sounds, especially in a second language.
- **Solution:** Incorporate phonics activities, rhyming games, and repetition to help develop auditory discrimination skills.

4. Lack of Motivation or Interest

- **Challenge:** If listening tasks are not engaging or relevant, learners may lose interest quickly.
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- **Solution:** Use topics and materials that are age-appropriate and align with their interests, such as cartoons, animals, or favorite stories. Make activities interactive and fun.

5. Over-Reliance on Native Language

- **Challenge:** Young learners might rely heavily on their first language, making it harder for them to immerse in listening activities.
- **Solution:** Create an immersive environment by using the target language consistently, but ensure instructions are clear and supported with non-verbal cues.

6. Anxiety and Lack of Confidence

- **Challenge:** Some young learners may feel overwhelmed or shy about understanding and responding to spoken language.
- **Solution:** Build a supportive atmosphere. Praise their efforts, encourage participation, and avoid putting pressure on immediate correctness.

7. Technical and Logistical Issues

- **Challenge:** Poor audio quality, inappropriate pacing of listening materials, or a lack of suitable resources can hinder effective listening practice.
- **Solution:** Choose high-quality, age-appropriate resources with clear audio. Adjust the speed of speech if necessary and ensure classroom technology is reliable.

8. Limited Assessment Tools

- **Challenge:** Assessing listening skills in young learners can be difficult, as traditional methods may not capture their progress effectively.
- **Solution:** Use informal, interactive assessments such as asking questions about a story, playing "listen and do" games, or observing their reactions during activities.

9. Cultural and Contextual Challenges

- **Challenge:** Young learners might find it hard to relate to or understand materials based on unfamiliar cultural contexts.
- **Solution:** Incorporate culturally relevant materials or adapt content to make it relatable and understandable.

10. Balancing Listening with Other Skills

- **Challenge:** Listening activities might not always integrate well with speaking, reading, or writing practice.
- **Solution:** Design holistic lessons where listening tasks lead to speaking opportunities, storytelling, or creative expression.

In conclusion, Teaching listening skills to young EFL learners, particularly in contexts like Indonesia, involves addressing various challenges that stem from linguistic, cognitive, and environmental factors. Limited vocabulary, difficulty in differentiating sounds, and reliance on native language are significant obstacles that hinder listening comprehension. Moreover, young learners' short attention spans and their need for engaging, culturally relevant materials further complicate the process. As emphasized by Brown (2007), teaching listening requires more than linguistic rules; it necessitates fostering spontaneous and meaningful communication. Nunan (2002) highlights listening as an essential skill for developing spoken language proficiency, which demands active interaction between teachers and students. Strategies such as pre-teaching vocabulary, using multimedia resources, employing both top-down and bottom-up processing techniques, and creating supportive, immersive environments can address these challenges effectively. By selecting appropriate materials and methods tailored to students' levels and needs, teachers can build their learners' confidence and competence in listening. This, in turn, lays a strong foundation for holistic language development and helps learners become proficient in using English for meaningful communication.

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